

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Integrated Thermal Energy Storage within Adiabatic Compressed Air Energy Storage System
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	ITES-ACAES
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	KTH, Royal Institute of Technology
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Compressed Air Energy Storage, Thermal Energy Storage, Computational Fluid Dynamics
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	01/02/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	14/04/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	06/02/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	14/04/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	22
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekends / Bank Holidays
Number of days using the RI	48
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	<p>The work proposed concerns adiabatic compressed air energy storage (ACAES) and thermal energy storage (TES) units and how they can be better integrated to improve the overall efficiency of the system. The study was to use CFD modelling of TES units and seeing how they perform using varied materials/heat exchangers. This will then feed into the overall performance of the ACAES system with results from Lee's other work on LPGC/E. All thermal energy storage work will</p>

be validated from previous work at KTH and future lab testing with the experimental TES rigs that are in place at KTH.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

Three dimensional CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulations of a Liquid Piston Gas Compressor/Expander (LPGC/E) to understand how various heat exchangers perform against the baseline case. This full arrangement is simulated to investigate the physics and fluid-structure interaction, which will provide a greater understanding of this process.

Once the final temperatures are found from these simulations the numbers will be used to then work out which PCM will work best for this application, then also which geometry will work best with this PCM. Leading to an optimal thermal energy storage unit. Several types of heat exchanger-based TES for efficient heat extraction in the TES integrated CAES project concept. Studies performed on the testing of different heat exchanger designs with developed infrastructure at KTH, shell and tube heat exchanger design and submerged finned pipe heat exchanger.

Also, research has taken place on potentially insulating the compression unit with PCMs so that any heat lost through the cylinder wall could be captured.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Liquid Piston Gas Compressor results show that by applying various heat exchangers (aluminium) inside the compression cylinder that the temperature can be reduced producing a near-isothermal process. By reducing this air temperature on the inside the efficiency of the compression process should increase but by reducing the air temperature inside the cylinder when this leaves the PCM needed to capture the heat from the air being stored does not have to have a high melting point, which narrows down the materials that can be chosen for this TES unit. This compression chamber used is a small-scale cylinder, which is 0.079m (internal diameter) by 1m (height). By compressing the air from 2.5 to 10 bar (2.5 bar pumps input pressure for the experimental work being undertaken in Manchester) and starting with an initial air temperature of 298K, by applying various heat exchanger/porous media the air temperature can be reduced to 315K.

For simulations involving the Thermal Energy Storage (TES) unit and Phase Change Materials (PCM) the simulations proved more difficult. Heat transfer simulations with the PCM was a challenge due to the melting/solidification points and the hysteresis. The more that PCMs were researched the more parameters had to be considered for the simulations, so it was a case of starting with a few then building then up after a number of trial simulations. At first it was easier to investigate using PCM for higher temperature heat transfer using molten salt as a PCM, this provided the initial results. This could be used for large-scale Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) systems. On a small-scale it proved more difficult due to the speed at which the air would leave the compression chamber and if the PCM could capture the heat in such a short space of time. Something that is still being investigated.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

For the LPGC/E simulations, it shows that by using various aluminium heat exchangers, the final air temperature can be reduced in a LPGC. The results show different levels of reduction depending on the geometries used. The heat exchangers used are parallel plates and interrupted plates (200mm & 400mm). These plates do not change in volume but by changing the

arrangement provides better heat transfer attributes. The interrupted plates still provide a channel flow but reducing the plate's lengths and stacking them this increased the surface area, promotes mixing, and also breaks up the viscous sublayer of flow (as opposed to parallel plates), all of which increase the heat transfer. This shows that geometry plays a major role in the heat transfer aspect. Potentially changing the material from aluminium to something with a higher thermal conductivity these temperatures could be further reduced. This all leads into then material selection and size needed for TES unit as they are interlinked. By reducing the temperature as much as possible means using a PCM with a lower melting and solidification points, maybe leading to the use of organic materials.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Working PCM simulations were challenging as I have not worked with PCMs before, so once I had conducted a literature review on how they work and their characteristics, I began work on the CFD simulations. This proved difficult with the melting/solidification points and the hysteresis.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

As this was all computational work all I needed was a computer and software. Had no issues with facilities, equipment etc. Was provided a desktop on campus and also had my own university issued laptop from Manchester.

Difficulty was getting the work complete in such a short space of time. I was able to complete compression simulations to see what the final air temperature was when leaving the compression chamber, but the heat transfer simulations with the PCM was a challenge, due to the issues above.

The more that PCMs were researched the more parameters had to be considered for the simulations, so it was a case of starting with a few then building then up after a number of trial simulations.

Intended publications

There is still ongoing work that needs to be done for the TES/PCM work but potentially publish at a conference or in an Energy Storage journal. Details to be confirmed.

Work undertaken for compression of air in LPGC is to be presented at IGEC 2023 (<https://www.iagenet.org/igec2023>) in Glasgow in July 2023, with the aim of potentially publishing one of the energy journals there or to publish later on in a fluid/heat transfer journal.

Data management

Data Manager: X.Y@manchester.ac.uk

Project data is stored in multiple places. I have made copies which are stored on my University of Manchester OneDrive, then jobs that are running are stored in my storage folder after running jobs on the HPC's. And when the jobs are complete a copy is placed on my USB drive.

Conclusions / additional comments

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details.				

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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<i>[Comment]</i>											

Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>											
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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<i>[Please provide details]</i>											

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.